

ORGANIZATION OF CHEMISTRY CLASSES THROUGH MODULAR SYSTEM

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Annotation: *This article discusses the importance of planning the use of modular systems in teaching chemistry and modular lessons.*

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Development of a modular training program aimed at the formation of competence is a very complex task, which requires from its developers scientific-practical and psychological-pedagogical competence.

When preparing a module program on the subject and the organization of the lesson within the modular teaching, it is advisable to follow the following:

- the name of the module should be short and clear;
- Demonstration of competence formed as a result of studying the module;
- substantiation and demonstration of a level of development-appropriate competence;
- availability of entrance tests to determine the level of competence formed;
- coverage of methods of activation of personal experience;
- Development of methods for discussing and analyzing the activated experience;
- Demonstration of theoretical knowledge that develops competence, substantiation of forms of its delivery;
- the need for exit tests to determine the development of "personal participation" in new experiments, practical tasks, competencies.

Professional training of chemistry teachers is a multi-stage process that requires the continuous formation of students' special competencies in the learning process. At each stage, issues of special competence development are identified, which should correspond to the level of professional training of chemistry teachers in higher education.

The uniqueness of chemistry as a subject lies in the existence of its large conceptual apparatus - concepts, laws and regulations, theoretical foundations, and they are formed in the process of studying the sections of the subject, step by step.

In addition, chemistry is a subject, the basis of which is chemistry, and it studies the structure, composition, properties of substances, the process of transformation from one type to another and has a practical significance, in other words, this subject is widely used in our daily lives. It is used, as well as its achievements are widely used in the training of a number of specialists, in scientific areas.

Thus, in the process of studying chemistry, there are opportunities to form not only chemical knowledge, but also general and special skills, including research skills.

Content of education, it is a goal, the implementation of which is the responsibility of the institution to the future specialist. The content of training serves to achieve this goal. The content of teaching is a means of its purpose in relation to the content of education.

Modular training- based on the content of teaching forms, such as curriculum, syllabus, textbook, manual, didactic material, teacher information. In order to implement the content of educational modular training is formed in the form of educational information and complex issues, tasks, exercises that provide the opportunity to master the system of professional and personal qualities, worldview, skills and abilities.

The new technological (modular) approach requires new technological directions:

- The focus is on the student's learning activities (educational success in any case depends on the effectiveness of educational activities);
- diagnostics of expediency and objective control of results;
- Integrity of the educational process as a pedagogical system;
- Pre-planning of the educational process.

The effective mastering of the module depends not only on the method of presenting the teaching material, but also on the qualifications of the teacher and the development and content of complex issues. The main structural unit of the content of any subject is the issue (task).

For the learner, it (problem, task) is an illustration of the theory, the ability to solve a practical situation, an exercise in testing certain methods, a tool for evaluating and analyzing the results of learning activities.

A modular approach to education requires a change in the content, purpose and management of teaching.

In the scientific and pedagogical literature, the classification of didactic goals is manifested in two directions: at the level (general pedagogical, subject, operative) and in didactic functions (cognitive and operational). The multilevel nature of learning objectives is defined as follows:

- Level 1: operational learning objectives of specific types of courses;
- Level 2: learning objectives of the subject;
- Level 3: general pedagogical goals of teaching.

The content of general pedagogical goals (level 3) is represented by the model or qualification description (characteristic) of the specialist and constitutes general and special knowledge, skills and personality traits.

The learning objectives of the subject (subject) (level 2) represent the content and specificity of the subject. Level 2 of the goal in modular learning is called the complex didactic goal and it is implemented in the whole module program.

In a specific type of training (level 1), operational goals are formed in knowledge, skills, intellectual operations, socio-communicative skills, and this allows for a clear organization of educational activities.

The modular approach is integrated into the level of operational goals and is tailored to specific goals. The integrated target is implemented by a clear module.

In some cases, the integrated goal includes the following complex didactic objectives:

Didactic purpose, It is the creation of conditions for self-development, self-improvement, self-realization, self-expression of the student, as well as the satisfaction of everyone's interests and tendencies, needs. providing is understood.

Educational purpose- to create conditions for the formation of the studied concepts and phenomena.

Developmental goal- to create conditions for the development of skills of independent work with various sources of information, the correct assessment of himself and his peers, as well as control over working hours.

Each integrated didactic goal consists of four specific didactic goals. The implementation of specific objectives consists of specific learning elements that make up the module.

So, the pyramid is built for the purposes of modular learning technologies:

- The upper part of the pyramid is a complex didactic goal (KDM) for the module program;
- intermediate level - if there are integrated didactic objectives (IDM) for module construction;
- low level - has special didactic objectives (XDM) for building learning elements.

The principle of complex, integrated and special integration of didactic goals is the guiding principle in modular teaching. The solution of specific didactic goals (XDM) provides a clear modular solution of integrated didactic goals (IDM).

The integrated didactic objectives (IDM) solution of all modules ensures the achievement of complex didactic objectives (KDM).

The content of the main learning elements should be considered in the theoretical and practical blocks of the module:

- The theoretical block stores the study material in a concentrated form and ends in the form of a summary - a generalization of the content of the module in an easy-to-remember form, for example, in the form of a basic abstract;

- The practical block includes exercises for learning new concepts and skills, as well as algorithms for solving them, or "basics of action", practical problems, their alternative solutions, test exercises with varying degrees of difficulty, "rating". The compiler includes compact exercises and a list of recommended literature.

The functionality of the training module is determined by the fact that its content is formed from the practical naming of the studied information. Movement activity and its limits are determined by the need for the material being studied. The module is divided into information and technological parts.

The information part of the module forms its functional blocks and it should require the knowledge and skills learned in connection with the next action. Therefore, another parallel name for modular learning is called block-modular learning and they are used as synonyms.

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